

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Biodiversity impact database including characterization factors and documentation ready for use in Module C

Deliverable 2.4

Summary

Work Package	2
Deliverable N°	2.4
Dissemination Level	ii. Public
Type	i. Data
Lead Partner	UFMG
Due Date	April 30, 2024
Submission Date	April 30, 2024
Status	Final
Authors	Ubirajara Oliveira
Other contributions	Andrea Pacheco

About CLEVER

Project Number	101060765
Project Title	CLEVER: Creating leverage to enhance biodiversity outcomes of global biomass trade
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-15
Start date	1 st September 2022
End date	31 st August 2025
Coordinator	RHEINISCHE FRIEDRICH-WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAT BONN

This document has been prepared in the framework of the project CLEVER. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This project has received funding from the European Research Executive Agency under HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions, grant agreement n°101060765

Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
INTRODUCTION	5
OBJECTIVES	5
METHODS	5
RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	5
CONCLUSION.....	8
PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED	8

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this deliverable we use the models to estimate biodiversity loss due to changes in land use, and the estimates of species richness, endemism, and species composition to analyze the loss of biodiversity associated with land use in different ecoregions, biomes and countries.

We produce the data necessary to calculate the characterization factors, essential to quantify the potential impact of different types and intensities of land use on biodiversity loss. This involved testing these impacts using our biodiversity models and synthesizing the results in tables that summarize impacts by spatial aggregations such as countries and ecoregions.

Our results will be used in Module C of the CLEVER project, providing estimates of land use impacts.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture-related activities have been identified as one of the major drivers of global biodiversity loss¹⁻³. The transformation of forests, savannas, and other ecosystems into areas of agricultural production not only causes the direct loss of species through habitat destruction but, it also threatens the loss of vital ecosystem functions such as nutrient cycles and hydrological dynamics, as well as functions like pollination and natural pest control^{1,3}. Thus, the quantification of these impacts is paramount to mitigating further biodiversity loss, as well as ensuring sustainable provision of food for all in the future^{4,5}.

However, accurately quantifying the impacts of agriculture and livestock on biodiversity is a complex challenge, in large part, due to the lack of data on biodiversity. This lack of data results in significant data gaps, which hinder the accurate assessment of the effects of these practices in different ecosystems and periods. Large parts of the world are undersampled or not monitored at all, while others may be overrepresented, leading to a distorted understanding of the real extent of environmental damage⁶⁻⁹. These challenges underscore the urgent need for more robust and representative data made available in order to improve this state of knowledge.

Here, building up from the work previously established in **D.2.2-2.3**, we **1**) summarize the methodology we developed in order to better quantify the impacts of agriculture and livestock, on biodiversity (including intensity of use), and **2**) translate the results of these modeling efforts which indicate current patterns of biodiversity indicators in both South America and Africa (as well as potential biodiversity loss) to data inputs to be further used in CLEVER.

The approaches presented here that have been under development throughout **D2.2-2.3** have wide potential for applications; from providing valuable insights into the ongoing biodiversity decline, to generating predictions of biodiversity patterns under various future scenarios including agricultural expansion, intensification, climate change, and deforestation.

OBJECTIVES

The objective of this work is to use the previously generated insights regarding the magnitude and spatial patterns of biodiversity loss in South America and Africa, and associate these with the impacts from different land uses and their intensities. In turn, this would enable the biodiversity indicators to be associated with the impacts of non-food biomass trade in further CLEVER analyses.

METHODS

As described in **D2.2-2.3**, to estimate the loss of biodiversity due to changes in land use, we built two models of biodiversity based on estimates of species richness and endemism. Here, we used these estimates to determine the effect of agriculture, cattle, and urban areas on reducing biodiversity. In close coordination with the UPV and BC3 project partners, we used these estimates of biodiversity loss (richness, endemism), paired with data on land use and ecoregions^{10,11} to generate the data required for the analyses to be carried out in Module C. To supplement and validate these results, we conducted statistical analyses

Characterization factors

Characterization factors (CF) – essential components of Life-Cycle Analyses (LCAs) – are numerical values that represent the potential impact of a certain activity or process on the environment. In the context of CLEVER, we used the mean difference between the baseline and the current biodiversity scenario in order to estimate the impacts of different land uses and intensities on said biodiversity, aggregating results per biome and ecoregion¹¹. We made these estimated impacts on biodiversity – i.e., average species loss/average loss of endemism per ecoregion, biome, and land-use and respective intensity of land use – available to CLEVER partners in a summarized table. This data will be used as a part of further Life-Cycle Analyses in Module C (available at <https://zenodo.org/records/11085529>, see example in Results and Discussion below).

Statistical validation: effects of land use and land use intensity on biodiversity

Going beyond producing these data, we validated the above results by statistically testing the association of the different land uses (and land use intensities) on our different biodiversity indicators. To this end, we created samples throughout our study area by taking equidistant points (5 km). We used generalized linear models (GLM), where each of the dimensions of biodiversity was used as a dependent variable, and 1 – land use type¹⁰, 2 - country, 3 - ecoregions¹¹, 4 - number of cattle heads/km²¹², 5 - percentage of agricultural area in 0.025° pixels¹³ were used as independent variables. These results further validated our expectations that different land uses have significant impacts on biodiversity loss/change (see Figs 1-2).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Statistical validation: effects of land use and land use intensity on biodiversity

In all tests carried out, both agricultural land uses (number of cattle heads/km² and percentage of agricultural area in 0.025° pixels) were significantly ($p < 0.01$) related to the reduction in species richness, endemism, and beta-diversity. We did not find a statistically significant reduction of species richness or endemism of urban land use. All countries, and more than 90% of biomes and ecoregions presented results significantly related to the reduction in the three dimensions of biodiversity. GLM results indicate that forest, cropland, and pasture areas are associated with a significant reduction in species richness ($p < 0.001$). Specifically, forests show greater loss of richness compared with pasture areas. Moreover, our results indicate that fires, cultivated areas, and livestock significantly decreased species richness ($p < 0.001$) (see Zenodo repository available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/11085529>).

In terms of endemism, the model suggests that the use of land for agriculture is significantly associated with the loss of endemism, with substantial negative impacts. Fires also showed a significant negative effect ($p < 0.001$). These results are consistent across various models, indicating the consistency of the observed trends.

Figure 1. Biodiversity loss by land use. (A) species richness loss (B) endemism loss (C) species composition change. Asterisk indicates significance ($p < 0.05$) in the GLM test in the relationships between biodiversity loss and land use.

Figure 2. Biodiversity loss by intensity of use (A) species richness loss (B) endemism loss (C) species composition change. We do not find statistically significant impacts of cattle or cropland intensity on any of the three biodiversity indicators.

Data made available for the calculation of characterization factors

CFs provide a measure of the environmental impact on biodiversity by quantifying the potential extinction threat to a species in a given area due to human activities¹⁴. Here, we provide these impacts by countries, biomes and ecoregions, presenting the average loss in the number of species (richness), reduction in the endemism index and percentage of change in species composition by contrasting the biodiversity estimates in the baseline and in the current scenario. Results are also disaggregated by crop and cattle intensity of use, respectively. Richness and endemism values for the current scenario and baseline are also presented. See **Fig. 3** for an example.

CNTRY_NAME	ECO_NAME	BIOME_NAME	REALM	Land_Use	fire	Cattle	Cattle intensity	Cropland	Cropland intensity	Beta_loss	Rich_loss	Rich_curre	Rich_base	Ende_curre	Ende_base	Ende_loss
Algeria	West Saharan woodlands	Deserts & montane xeric Shrublands	Palaearctic	Pasture	0.0	0.0	NO USE	0.0	NO USE	0.4	1826.4	1123.8	2950.3	0.0	0.0	0.0
Angola	Central African mangroves	Mangroves	Afrotropic	Forest	0.0	0.0	NO USE	0.0	NO USE	0.5	1826.9	2924.1	4751.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Argentina	Rock and Ice	N/A	N/A	Forest	0.0	0.0	NO USE	0.0	NO USE	1.0	2167.3	2705.6	4872.9	0.1	0.2	0.2

Figure 3. Illustrative example of table to be used in calculating characterization factors. Here, only three countries are shown, for illustrative purposes. Full dataset is available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/11085529>.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we estimated the impacts of land use and land use intensity on species richness, endemism, and composition. Thereby, we generated the data necessary for calculating characterization factors and have made them easily accessible to project partners to be further used in Module C towards the goal of improving our understanding of different supply-chain impacts on diverse biodiversity indicators.

PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

We have now generated the biodiversity impacts data that will be used for Module C (available at <https://zenodo.org/records/11085529>).

Moreover, the methods underlying the data provided here have now been published (i.e., the challenge of modeling biodiversity despite a lack of data). The article is available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/jbi.14851>.

REFERENCES

1. Rigal, S. *et al.* Farmland practices are driving bird population decline across Europe. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **120**, (2023).
2. Harfoot, M. B. J. *et al.* Using the IUCN Red List to map threats to terrestrial vertebrates at global scale. *Nat Ecol Evol* **5**, 1510–1519 (2021).
3. Li, B. V. & Jiang, B. Responses of forest structure, functions, and biodiversity to livestock disturbances: A global meta-analysis. *Glob Chang Biol* **27**, 4745–4757 (2021).
4. Kastner, T. *et al.* Global agricultural trade and land system sustainability: Implications for ecosystem carbon storage, biodiversity, and human nutrition. *One Earth* **4**, 1425–1443 (2021).
5. Juffe-Bignoli, D. *et al.* Mitigating the Impacts of Development Corridors on Biodiversity: A Global Review. *Front Ecol Evol* **9**, (2021).
6. Oliveira, U. *et al.* The strong influence of collection bias on biodiversity knowledge shortfalls of Brazilian terrestrial biodiversity. *Divers Distrib* **22**, 1232–1244 (2016).
7. Cardoso, P., Erwin, T. L., Borges, P. A. V & New, T. R. The seven impediments in invertebrate conservation and how to overcome them. *Biol Conserv* **144**, 2647–2655 (2011).
8. Brito, D. Overcoming the Linnean shortfall: Data deficiency and biological survey priorities. *Basic Appl Ecol* **11**, 709–713 (2010).
9. Bini, L. M., Diniz-Filho, J. A. F., Rangel, T. F. L. V. B., Bastos, R. P. & Pinto, M. P. Challenging Wallacean and Linnean shortfalls: knowledge gradients and conservation planning in a biodiversity hotspot. *Divers Distrib* **12**, 475–482 (2006).
10. Winkler, K., Fuchs, R., Rounsevell, M. & Herold, M. Global land use changes are four times greater than previously estimated. *Nat Commun* **12**, 2501 (2021).
11. Bailey, R. G. *Ecoregions*. (Springer New York, New York, NY, 2014). doi:10.1007/978-1-4939-0524-9.
12. Gilbert, M. *et al.* Global distribution data for cattle, buffaloes, horses, sheep, goats, pigs, chickens and ducks in 2010. *Sci Data* **5**, 180227 (2018).
13. Potapov, P. *et al.* Global maps of cropland extent and change show accelerated cropland expansion in the twenty-first century. *Nat Food* **3**, 19–28 (2021).
14. Chaudhary, A. & Brooks, T. M. Land Use Intensity-Specific Global Characterization Factors to Assess Product Biodiversity Footprints. *Environ Sci Technol* **52**, 5094–5104 (2018).

